

1-D Reflection-Refraction in Terms of Conservation of Probability and Particle Number

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In (1), the problem of one dimensional reflection-refraction is considered in terms of continuity of the photon electric field at an n_1 - n_2 (index of refraction) point. From Maxwell's equations, the electric field of a photon behaves as $\cos(-\omega t + kx)$, but $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ is used to simplify the math. It is then argued that the electric field and its first derivative must be continuous at the junction point of n_1 - n_2 which is taken to be $x=0$. These two equations allow one to solve for the coefficient of the reflected and refracted electric fields in terms of the incident electric field (whose weight we take to be 1). One may then combine the two equations to obtain a conservation of particle number equation: $AA/c_1 = BB/c_1 + CC/c_2$ ((1)) where c_1 is the speed in n_1 , c_2 in n_2 and AA , BB and CC are fluxes of the incident, reflected and refracted photons.

Here we argue that one may solve this problem strictly in terms of conservation. The conservation of particle number ((1)) is an obvious equation of conservation, but there are two unknowns if $A=1$ and the problem cannot be solved. This seems to suggest a second conservation equation, we argue. To find this conservation law, we note that there is a probability associated with free particles if one considers that a 2-body collision which is elastic has equal product probability for energy and momentum outcomes e_i, e_j and p_{xi}, p_{xj} if $e_i + e_j = e_1 + e_2$ and $p_{xi} + p_{xj} = p_{x1} + p_{x2}$, where e_1, e_2 and p_{x1}, p_{x2} are the initial values. This leads to a probability $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ which we argue must also be conserved across the junction point. We link this probability to $A \exp(-iEt + ipx)$ where $A \cdot A = \text{flux}$ in the case of problems containing flux. We then show that one may solve for B and C from these two conservation equations without resort to the continuity of the first derivative equation or argument that one must have mathematical continuity of the electric field across the n_1 - n_2 junction point. In other words, the problem may be seen entirely as a conservation one, but based on two conservation ideas.

Conservation of Probability and Particle Number

If an incoming photon has a probability to reflect and refract at an n_1 - n_2 junction (n_i = index of refraction), then it seems there should be conservation of particle number. Writing this in terms of flux:

$$AA/c_1 = BB/c_1 + CC/c_2 \quad ((1))$$

were c_i =speed in n_i and AA, BB, CC are fluxes of the incident, reflected and refracted photons.

This seems like an obvious equation, but unfortunately even setting $A=1$, one cannot solve for B and C . Nevertheless, ((1)) is a physical conservation equation. We argue that this seems to imply that there should be a second conservation equation present, but it is not clear what this should be. We note that $E = p_1 c_1 = p_2 c_2$ and that E energy is conserved throughout.

We suggest that there is a probability associated with a free particle because given a 2-body elastic collision, one does not know the outcomes (even if they conserve energy and

momentum). A statistical manner of dealing with this issue is to assume equal product probability for all pairs conserving energy and momentum.

Free Particle Probability

If two free particles with energy e_1, e_2 and momentum p_1, p_2 collide elastically, one knows that for the outcome:

$$E_1 + e_2 = e_i + e_j \quad \text{and} \quad p_1 + p_2 = p_x + p_j \quad ((2))$$

There are, however, multiple e_i, e_j and p_x, p_j pairs and one does not know which one to choose. We have suggested in previous notes that one may assign equal probability to all pairs which obey conservation. Given that one has free particles, one has no real value weight for a single 2-body collision. Thus, one expects a complex probability with modulus 1, i.e.

$$\exp(i C_1 e) \exp(i C_2 p_x) \quad ((3))$$

One cannot have p and $-p$ yield different probabilities so one requires p be multiplied by a measure which changes sign when the x -axis changes direction. This suggests that one has:

$$\exp(i p \Delta x) \quad ((4))$$

One may go further and suggest Lorentz invariance or:

$$\exp(-iEt + ipx) \quad ((5))$$

Thus, we suggest that there is a complex probability associated with free particles and that probability must also be conserved in a problem, not just particle number. We further suggest that ((5)) applies to photons due to its link with special relativity.

The 1-D Reflection-Refraction Problem

For a single 2-body collision, one may use the probability $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$. In the 1-D reflection-refraction problem, one does not have a single 2-body collision, but rather incident, reflected and refracted photons. We note that if one takes the modulus of ((5)) one has 1, which suggests equal probability for a collision at point x . We suggest that this means in a unit time and so 1 should really be linked with flux in the 1-D reflection problem. Thus, one really has:

$$A \exp(-iEt + ipx) \quad \text{where} \quad A^*A = \text{the incident flux for the incident photon} \quad ((6))$$

One may now introduce a conservation of probability law at the $x=0$ n_1 - n_2 junction, i.e.

$$A \exp(ip) + B \exp(-ipx) = C \exp(ip_2x) \quad \text{where} \quad x=0 \quad ((7))$$

This yields $A+B=C$. Setting $A=1$, one has: $1+B=C$ ((8))

One may now use ((8)) and ((1)) to solve the problem. One does not have to worry about mathematical continuity of wavefunctions at the junction problem (although this is fine), but rather may think of the problem in an entirely physical way as being based on conservation. Using $c_i = c/n_i$:

$$B n_1 + (1+B) n_2 = n_1 \quad ((9a)) \text{ and } (C-1) n_1 + C n_2 = n_1 \quad ((9b))$$

Both of these may be solved as quadratic equations. ((9a)) yields:

$$B = \frac{1}{(n_1+n_2)} \{-n_2 + \sqrt{n_2^2 + (n_1+n_2)(n_1-n_2)}\} = \frac{(n_1-n_2)}{(n_1+n_2)} \quad ((10a))$$

$$C(n_1+n_2) - 2n_1 = 0 \text{ or } C = \frac{2n_1}{(n_1+n_2)} \quad ((10b))$$

These are the same values obtained using the continuity of electric field approach of (1).

Conclusion

In conclusion, (1) solves the 1-D reflection-refraction problem by imposing continuity of the electric field of a photon and its first derivative at an n_1 - n_2 (index of refraction) junction. From Maxwell's equations for a photon, a photon electric field is proportional to $\cos(-\omega t + px)$ and $\exp(-iEt + px)$ is used for simplicity ($\hbar=1$). The two equations then combine to yield conservation of photon number: $AA/c_1 = BB/c_1 + CC/c_2$ where $c_i=c/n_i$ and AA, BB, CC are incident, reflected and refracted fluxes.

We suggest that one may solve this problem entirely in terms of the notion of conservation. The first conservation law is: $AA/c_1 = BB/c_1 + CC/c_2$, but it is not clear what the second is. We suggest that a single free particle is linked with a complex probability $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ which ensures that in 2-body elastic collisions with e_1, e_2 and p_1x, p_2x as initial values, that any e_i, e_j and p_1x, p_2x pairs which satisfy $e_1+e_2=e_i+e_j$ and $p_1x+p_2x = p_1x+p_2x$ have the same weight. This probability then must be conserved in a problem. If one considers the modulus of such a free particle probability, it is 1 meaning that one has equal probability for an interaction at any x presumably in a Δt . For problems with fluxes, as in the 1-D reflection-refraction case, we suggest that the quantity to consider is $\text{flux} \cdot 1$ so $A \exp(-iEt + ipx)$ is the appropriate probability where $A \cdot A = \text{flux}$. The conservation of probability in such a case is then: $A \exp(ipx) + B \exp(-ipx) = C \exp(ipx)$ at $x=0$, the n_1 - n_2 junction. The two conservation equations then may be used to solve for $B = (n_1-n_2)/(n_1+n_2)$ and $C = 2n_1/(n_1+n_2)$, the same result as the continuity of electric field approach of (1).

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Reflection_phase_change